

FTIR-Based Comparative Study of *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh) leaves from Rajmahal Hills, Jharkhand for Phytochemical Constituents Evaluation

Anil Kumar*¹, Dharmendra Kumar Yadav², Ashwaraya Prakash³, Rishav Raj⁴,
Richa Bharti⁴, Lazor Murmu⁴

¹H.O.D., P. G. Dept. of Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj, S.K.M.U, Dumka

²Asst. Prof. P.G. Dept. of Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj, S.K.M.U, Dumka

³P.G Scholar, P.G. Dept. of Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj, S.K.M.U, Dumka

⁴U.G Scholar, P.G. Dept. of Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj, S.K.M. U, Dumka

ABSTRACT

Andrographis paniculata (Kalmegh) is an important medicinal plant widely used in traditional and modern medicine for liver disorders, infections, antiviral, neuroprotective disorder, anti-cancer, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory. The present study focused on the combined evaluation of morphological characteristics and phytochemical constituent of Kalmegh collected from the Rajmahal Hills region of Sahibganj (Medicinal Hub), Jharkhand. The plant samples showed distinct regional features such as moderate height (40–90 cm), dark green leaves and strong bitterness. These characteristics indicate the presence of rich bioactive compounds, especially andrographolide and phenolic compounds. Methanolic and ethanolic extracts of the plant were prepared and analysed using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy in the range of 4000–500 cm^{-1} . The FTIR spectra revealed the presence of important functional groups such as O–H, C–H, C=O and C–O, which correspond to phenols, flavonoids, diterpenoids, glycosides andrographolide (medicinal compound). A comparative analysis showed that the ethanolic extract exhibited stronger, sharper and more complex peaks compared to the methanolic extract, especially in the fingerprint region. This indicates that ethanol is a more efficient solvent for extracting bioactive compounds. Ethanol is safe for human consumption and preferred solvent for food, beverages and traditional medicines than Methanol. Also, Ethanol extract exhibit a broader, more balanced range of bioactive compounds like phenolic, flavonoids and andrographolide. Methanol often extracts a high proportion of undesirable chlorophyll and non-polar compounds making the purification process more complex. The present study clearly shows that medicinal values of Kalmegh of the Rajmahal Hills influence both plant morphology and phytochemical richness. FTIR is proved to be a simple, rapid, and reliable method for plant analysis.

Keywords: *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh), FTIR, Rajmahal Hills, Phytochemicals, Ethanolic extract, Methanolic extract.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are very important for healthcare and drug development. *Andrographis paniculata* belongs to the family of Acanthaceae, commonly known as “Kalmegh” or “King of Bitters” due to its extremely bitter taste. The plant height is generally 40–90 cm, leaves were narrow and dark green in colour⁽¹⁾. It is widely used in traditional medicine due to its strong medicinal properties. The plant contains important bioactive compounds such as andrographolide,

flavonoids, phenolic compounds and glycosides⁽¹⁾. These compounds are responsible for antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-virus, anti-cancer, neuroprotective disorder and antiviral activities^(1–16). The study area Hathmari in (Fig. 1), Rajmahal Hills region of Sahibganj, Jharkhand, has unique environmental conditions such as rocky soil, moderate rainfall and warm climate. These conditions influence plant growth and increase the production of secondary metabolites.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Fig. 1: Google Image of Study Area.

FTIR spectroscopy is a simple and effective technique used to identify functional groups in plant extracts⁽¹⁷⁾. In this study, methanolic and ethanolic extracts of Kalmegh were analysed to identify phytochemicals and compare extraction efficiency. FTIR analysis revealed the presence of important functional groups and phytochemical constituents in both extracts. This study aims to analyse morphological characteristics of Kalmegh, identify phytochemicals using FTIR and Comparative study of methanolic and ethanolic extracts.

2. Materials And Methods: -

Equipment⁽¹⁸⁾

- Grinder (Morphy Richards)
- Electronic balance (DJ602A)
- Refrigerator (SAMSUNG)
- Hot air oven (OPTICS TECHNOLOGY)
- FTIR Spectrophotometer (INVENIO S, BRUKER OPTIK, GmbH)

Reagents and Chemicals⁽¹⁸⁾

- Sample Material – Dried Kalmegh Leaves

- Extraction Solvent – Methanol (HIMEDIA) & Ethanol (ZENHOL)

Consumables⁽¹⁸⁾

- Glassware – Reagent bottles, Measuring cylinder, Funnels, Watch glass, Beakers (BOROSIL)
- Filter papers
- Aluminium foil
- Protective Equipment – Apron, Gloves, Glass

2.1 Collection of Plant Material: -

Fresh and healthy leaves of *Andrographis paniculata* were collected (Fig. 2a) from the Hathmari that belongs to Rajmahal Hills region of Sahibganj, Jharkhand. The plant was identified based on leaf shape, stem structure and flower characteristics.

2.2 Drying and Powder Preparation: -

The leaves were washed with distilled water and dried under shade for 7–10 days (Fig. 2b). After drying, the leaves were grounded into fine powder and stored in airtight containers (Fig. 2c)^(18,19).

Fig. 2a: Kalmegh Leaves.

Fig. 2b: Dried Kalmegh Leaves.

Fig. 2c: Powder of Dried Kalmegh Leaves.

2.3 Preparation of Extracts: -

a) Kalmegh Methanolic Extract: -

The general method was used to prepare the extract of Kalmegh leaves. Approximately 20 g of Kalmegh leaves powder was transferred into a clean reagent bottle and soaked in 100 mL methanol for 48 hours at room temperature (Fig. 3a). After the extraction period, the mixture was filtered using Whatman filter paper to obtain the extract of Kalmegh leaves. The extract was collected and excess solvent was evaporated in hot air oven at 50°C to obtain the crude extract⁽¹⁸⁻²³⁾. To enhance the extraction efficiency, the extraction process was repeated three times using fresh solvent. The Stock Crude Methanolic Kalmegh leaves extract used for further FTIR spectral analysis.

Fig. 3a: Kalmegh Methanolic Extract.

Fig. 3b: Kalmegh Ethanolic Extract.

2.4 FTIR Spectrophotometer Analysis: -

FTIR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets using Bruker Optik (GmbH) FTIR spectrometer in the spectral range 4000-500 cm^{-1} at Department of Applied Geology, IIT(ISM), Dhanbad. The FTIR optical bench was flushed with nitrogen gas for 2

b) Kalmegh Ethanolic Extract: -

The general method was used to prepare the extract of Kalmegh leaves. Approximately 20 g of Kalmegh leaves powder was transferred into a clean reagent bottle and soaked in 100 mL ethanol for 48 hours at room temperature (Fig. 3b). After the extraction period, the mixture was filtered using Whatman filter paper to obtain the extract of Kalmegh leaves. The extract was collected and excess solvent was evaporated in hot air oven at 50°C to obtain the crude extract⁽¹⁸⁻²³⁾. To enhance the extraction efficiency, the extraction process was repeated three times using fresh solvent. The Stock Crude Ethanolic Kalmegh leaves extract used for further FTIR spectral analysis.

hours at a rate of approximately 200 liters/hr before analysis to minimize the effect of moisture and other gasses. Hydraulic press (~6 ton for 5 minutes) was used to make the KBr pellets using a mix of KBr powder (IR spectroscopy grade) and powdered samples (~200 mesh). The circular thin KBr pellets were inserted in the standard sample holder with a

quick lock base plate. The door of the sample analysis chamber was closed for analysis. The FTIR spectra was collected in absorbance/transmittance mode and saved as a separate file. The spectra were clipped for the desired frequency range (wave number: 4000-500 cm^{-1}) and baseline correction (rubber band correction)

was performed. The resultant FTIR data was plotted as absorbance/transmittance vs frequency plot (Y-X Plot).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION: -

Fig. 4: FTIR Spectral analysis of (a) Methanolic Extract Kalmegh and (b) Ethanolic Extract Kalmegh.

3.1 FTIR Spectral Analysis of Ethanolic & Methanolic Extract of Kalmegh: -

Table 1: Comparative FTIR Analysis of O–H Stretching Vibrations in Methanolic and Ethanolic Extracts of Kalmegh^(17,18,21,24)

Parameter	Methanolic Extract	Ethanolic Extract	Interpretation
Peak Position	~3320–3350 cm^{-1}	~3380–3420 cm^{-1}	Slight shift due to solvent polarity
Peak Shape	Broad	Very broad	Hydrogen bonding present
Peak Intensity	Moderate	Strong	Higher phenolic content in ethanol
Functional Group	O–H stretching	O–H stretching	Alcohols & Phenols
Chemical Compounds	Phenols	Phenols, Flavonoids	Bioactive compounds

Table 2: Comparative FTIR Analysis of Carbonyl (C=O) Stretching Vibrations in Methanolic and Ethanolic Extracts of Kalmegh^(17-19,21,24,25).

Parameter	Methanolic Extract	Ethanolic Extract	Interpretation
Peak Position	~1710–1730 cm ⁻¹	~1690–1720 cm ⁻¹	Slight shift due to interaction
Peak Shape	Weak and broad	Sharp and intense	Better resolution in ethanol
Peak Intensity	Low	High	Higher diterpenoid content
Functional Group	Carbonyl (C=O)	Carbonyl (C=O)	Aldehydes, Ketones
Chemical Compounds	Diterpenoids	Andrographolide	Active medicinal compound

Table 3: Comparative Characteristics of O–H and C=O Functional Group Peaks^(17-19,21,24,25).

Feature	O–H Peak (~3400 cm ⁻¹)	C=O Peak (~1700 cm ⁻¹)
Type of Bond	Hydrogen-bonded	Double bond
Functional Group	Alcohol/Phenol	Carbonyl
Compound Type	Phenols, Flavonoids	Diterpenoids
Peak Shape	Broad	Sharp
Importance	Antioxidant activity	Medicinal activity
Sensitivity	Sensitive to hydrogen bonding	Sensitive to molecular structure

Table 4: Comparative Extraction Efficiency and Phytochemical Profile of Methanolic & Ethanolic Extract of Kalmegh.

Parameter	Methanolic Extract	Ethanolic Extract
O–H Peak	Moderate	Strong
C=O Peak	Weak	Strong
Peak Clarity	Less clear	More clear
Fingerprint Region	Less complex	Highly complex
Overall Extraction	Moderate	High

3.2 FTIR Explanation of -OH Stretching: -

The O–H stretching peak appears as a broad band around 3400 cm⁻¹. This broadness is due to hydrogen bonding between molecules. The peak indicates the presence of phenolic compounds and alcohols, which are responsible for antioxidant activity^(17,21,24,26). In the Ethanolic extract, this peak is stronger and broader compared to Methanolic extract. This shows that ethanolic extracts possess more phenolic compounds. According to Harborne (1998), phenolic compounds play a key role in plant defence and medicinal activity (Table 1).

3.3 FTIR Explanation of C=O Stretching: -

The peak around 1700 cm⁻¹ represents C=O stretching, which is a characteristic feature of carbonyl compounds such as aldehydes, ketones and esters. In Kalmegh, this peak is mainly associated with andrographolide, a diterpenoid responsible for medicinal properties such as anti-inflammatory and antiviral activity^(17-19,21,24-26). The ethanolic extract shows a sharper and stronger peak, indicating higher concentration of andrographolide. Methanolic extract shows a weaker peak, suggesting lower extraction efficiency (Table 2).

3.4 FTIR Explanation of Major Peaks: -

O–H peak depicts about phenolic compounds (antioxidants) and the C=O peak depicts about

andrographolide (medicinal compound) presence in the methanolic and Ethanolic extract and also both peaks together confirm the medicinal value of Kalmegh (Table 3)^(17-19,21,24).

3.5 Comparative FTIR Explanation of Ethanolic & Methanolic Extract: -

The methanolic extract possess moderate O-H peak, weak -OH, moderate extraction of the compounds like diterpenoids which may be used for anti-inflammation, anti-cancer and antioxidant. While the Ethanolic extract possess strong -OH peak, C=O peak, high complex finger region and the extraction is high. Ethanolic extract of Kalmegh is more superior than Methanolic extract of Kalmegh (Table 4) may be due to clear fingerprint region more balanced range of bioactive compounds like phenols, flavonoids, andrographolide. While Methanolic extract of Kalmegh may use high proportion of undesirable chlorophyll, non-polar compounds making the process more complex. Hence Ethanolic extract of Kalmegh may be the better than Methanolic extract of Kalmegh and also Ethanolic extract are preferred solvent for food beverages and traditional medicine.

4.Applications Of *Andrographis Paniculata* (Kalmegh): -

The study shows that Kalmegh is a rich source of bioactive compounds such as andrographolide, phenols and flavonoids, which are responsible for its medicinal properties. FTIR analysis confirms the presence of important functional groups like O-H, C=O, and C-O, indicating antioxidant and therapeutic compounds^(17,18,26). The ethanolic extract shows stronger peaks compared to methanolic extract, suggesting better extraction efficiency. The strong bitterness of the plant collected from Rajmahal Hills also indicates high phytochemical content. Kalmegh is widely used as an antioxidant and antiviral agent and plays an important role in liver protection and immune system improvement. It is commonly used in herbal medicine and Ayurvedic formulations. In addition, it has potential applications in drug development, green synthesis of nanoparticles and advanced pharmaceutical research.

CONCLUSION: -

Ethanol is more effective in extracting phenolic compounds. Therefore, Ethanolic extracts contains more diterpenoid compounds as compared to Methanolic extract. The study confirms that *Andrographis paniculata* from Rajmahal Hills is rich in bioactive compounds. FTIR analysis successfully identified important functional groups such as phenolic compounds, flavonoids, diterpenoids and glycosides. The ethanolic extract showed stronger and clearer peaks compared to methanolic extract, proving its higher extraction efficiency. The FTIR spectral analysis of Kalmegh clearly shows the presence of important functional groups such as O-H and C=O, which correspond to phenolic and diterpenoids compounds. The detailed peak analysis confirms that, O-H peak indicates antioxidant compounds and C=O peak indicates andrographolide. Thus, ethanol is recommended as a better solvent, and FTIR is a reliable method for phytochemical analysis. FTIR is a reliable technique and ethanol is a suitable solvent for studying medicinal plants.

6. Scope Of Future Work: -

Future research on *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh) can focus on advanced techniques like GC-MS and HPLC for accurate identification of bioactive compounds. Studies on antioxidant and antimicrobial activities can provide scientific support for its medicinal use. Development of herbal formulations such as tablets and extracts can improve its practical applications. The plant can also be used for green synthesis of nanoparticles in eco-friendly technologies. Additionally, studying seasonal and geographical variations will help in identifying the best conditions for maximum phytochemical content and medicinal value.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: -

The authors express their profound gratitude to Prof. (Dr.) Kunal Kandir, Hon'ble Vice-Chancellor and Prof. (Dr.) Ram Kumar Singh, Hon'ble Vice-Chancellor (Presently Acting) of Sido Kanhu Murmu University, Dumka, Jharkhand for his constant encouragement and support in strengthening research and laboratory facilities. The authors are sincerely thankful to S. R.I. Rizvi, Principal of Sahibganj College, for his valuable guidance, inspiration and for providing the necessary academic environment for

this work. The authors gratefully acknowledge Dr. Anil Kumar, Head of the P.G. Department of Chemistry and Dharmendra Kumar Yadav for their constant guidance, academic support and insightful suggestions throughout the study. The authors gratefully acknowledge the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Government of India, under the DST-FIST Level-II Programme at the Department of Applied Geology, Indian Institute of Technology (Indian School of Mines) Dhanbad. The FTIR analysis was carried out using the advanced facility available through the I-STEM portal funded by the Office of the Principal Scientific Adviser, Government of India. The authors acknowledge to Prof. Anup Krishna Prasad, Department of Applied Geology, IIT (ISM), Dhanbad for their kind cooperation in characterization part. The authors acknowledge with appreciation the support and cooperation of Sumit Kumar Sharma, Sunil Kumar Yadav, Rahul Kumar Mirdha (Ph.D. Scholar), Niranjana Mishra (Ph.D. Scholar), Devvrat Kumar (M.Sc.), Abhishek Anand (M.Sc.), Vinay Kumar, Ankit Kumar Tanti and colleagues who have willingly helped out with their abilities. The author expresses sincere gratitude to all individuals and institutions that supported for this research work.

REFERENCES

1. Kumar V, Van Staden J. A Review of *Swertia chirayita* (Gentianaceae) as a Traditional Medicinal Plant. *Front Pharmacol.* 2016 Jan 12;6. doi:10.3389/fphar.2015.00308
2. Shivaji Banerjee SB, Sur TK, Suvra Mandal SM, Das PC, Sridhar Sikdar SS. Assessment of the anti-inflammatory effects of *Swertia chirata* in acute and chronic experimental models in male albino rats. *Vol. 32.* 2000;32(1):21–4.
3. Rai LK, Prasad P, Sharma E. Conservation threats to some important medicinal plants of the Sikkim Himalaya. *Biol Conserv.* 2000 Apr;93(1):27–33. doi:10.1016/S0006-3207(99)00116-0
4. Saha P, Mandal S, Das A, Das PC, Das S. Evaluation of the anticarcinogenic activity of *Swertia chirata* Buch.Ham, an Indian medicinal plant, on DMBA - induced mouse skin carcinogenesis model. *Phytotherapy Research.* 2004 May 26;18(5):373 – 8. doi:10.1002/ptr.1436
5. Chen Y, Huang B, He J, Han L, Zhan Y, Wang Y. In vitro and in vivo antioxidant effects of the ethanolic extract of *Swertia chirayita*. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2011 Jun;136(2):309–15. doi:10.1016/j.jep.2011.04.058
6. Schimmer O, Mauthner H. Polymethoxylated Xanthenes from the Herb of *Centaurium erythraea* with Strong Antimutagenic Properties in *Salmonella typhimurium*. *Planta Med.* 1996 Dec 4;62(06):561–4. doi:10.1055/s-2006-957973
7. Gopalkrishna V, Verma H, Patil P, Kolhapure R. Antiviral activity of the Indian medicinal plant extract, *Swertia chirata* against herpes simplex viruses: A study by in-vitro and molecular approach. *Indian J Med Microbiol.* 2008;26(4):322. doi:10.4103/0255-0857.43561
8. Alam KD, Ali MS, Parvin S, Mahjabeen S, Akbar MA, Ahamed R. In vitro Antimicrobial Activities of Different Fractions of *Swertia chirata* Ethanolic Extract. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences.* 2009 Sep 15;12(19):1334–7. doi:10.3923/pjbs.2009.1334.1337
9. Arya R, Sharma S, Singh S. Antidiabetic effect of Whole Plant Extract and Fractions of *Swertia chirayita* Buch.-Ham. *Planta Med.* 2011 Mar 21;77(05). doi:10.1055/s-0031-1273667
10. Kar A, Choudhary BK, Bandyopadhyay NG. Comparative evaluation of hypoglycaemic activity of some Indian medicinal plants in alloxan diabetic rats. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2003 Jan;84(1):105–8. doi:10.1016/S0378-8741(02)00144-7
11. Pal D, Sur S, Mandal S, Das A, Roy A, Das S, et al. Prevention of liver carcinogenesis by amarogentin through modulation of G 1 /S cell cycle check point and induction of apoptosis. *Carcinogenesis.* 2012 Dec;33(12):2424–31. doi:10.1093/carcin/bgs276
12. Verma VK, Sarwa KK, Kumar A, Zaman MdK. Comparison of hepatoprotective activity of *Swertia chirayita* and *Andrographis paniculata* plant of North–East India against CCl₄ induced hepatotoxic rats. *J Pharm Res.* 2013 Jul;7(7):647–53. doi:10.1016/j.jopr.2013.07.008
13. Saha P, Mandal S, Das A, Das S. Amarogentin can reduce hyperproliferation by downregulation of Cox-II and upregulation of apoptosis in mouse skin carcinogenesis model. *Cancer Lett.* 2006

- Dec;244(2):252–9.
doi:10.1016/j.canlet.2005.12.036
14. Kavimani S, Manisenthkumar KT. Effect of methanolic extract of *Enicostemma littorale* on Dalton's ascitic lymphoma. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2000 Jul;71(1–2):349–52. doi:10.1016/S0378-8741(00)00190-2
15. Guha S, Ghosal S, Chattopadhyay U. Antitumor, Immunomodulatory and Anti-HIV Effect of Mangiferin, a Naturally Occurring Glucosylxanthone. *Chemotherapy.* 2009 Sep 11;443–51. doi:10.1159/000239478
16. Bajpai M, Asthana R, Sharma N, Chatterjee S, Mukherjee S. Hypoglycemic Effect of Swerchirin from the Hexane Fraction of *Swertia chirayita*. *Planta Med.* 1991 Apr 5;57(02):102–4. doi:10.1055/s-2006-960041
17. Silverstein RM., Webster FX., Kiemle DJ., Bryce DL. *Spectrometric identification of organic compounds.* Wiley; 2017. 455 p.
18. Kumar A, Yadav DK, Raj R, Abdul M, Mahto RK. FTIR Studies of Bioactive Molecules in Methanolic Extract of *Azadirachta Indica* (Neem) Leaves. *Global Journal of Research in Medical Sciences.* 2026 Mar 27;6(2):20–6.
19. Kumar Yadav D, Bharitkar Y, Chatterjee K, Ghosh M, Mondal NB, Swarnakar S. Importance of Neem Leaf: An insight into its role in combating diseases. *Indian J Exp Biol.* 2016 Mar;54:708–18.
20. Hashim N, Abdullah S, Hassan L, Ghazali S, Jalil R. A study of neem leaves: Identification of method and solvent in extraction. *Mater Today Proc.* 2021 Mar;42. doi:10.1016/j.matpr.2020.11.726
21. Rani k. shameem, M.Mumtaj, Priyanka D, Chandran M. Phytochemical screening by FTIR spectroscopic analysis of methanol leaf extract of herb *Andrographis echiodides*. *Journal of Ayurvedic and Herbal Medicine.* 2021 Mar;7:257–61. doi:10.31254/jahm.2021.7408
22. Dikwa K, Alkali K, Ajibade G, Magaji Y, Ige O. Effects of Methanol Leaves Extracts of *Azadirachta indica* (Juss.), *Senna occidentalis* (Linn) and *Senna siamea* (Lam) on the In vitro Growth of *Plasmodium falciparum* (Laveran) Trophozoites. *Sahel Journal of Life Sciences FUDMA.* 2025 Mar;3:287–98. doi:10.33003/sajols-2025-0301-35
23. Yusuf A, Ajibade T, Oluwaseun E, Asenuga R, Onoja M, Akpan M, et al. Methanol leaf extract of *Azadirachta indica* mitigates isoproterenol-induced myocardial infarction through the modulation of oxidative stress, and PPAR α and BCL2 signaling in rats. *Avicenna J Phytomed.* 2025 Mar;15:1328–40. doi:10.22038/ajp.2024.25277
24. Kamble V, Gaikwad N. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy spectroscopic studies in *embelia ribes burm. F.*: A vulnerable medicinal plant. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2016 Mar;9:41. doi:10.22159/ajpcr.2016.v9s3.13804
25. Sarah R, Tabassum, Idrees N, Hussain M. Bioactive Compounds Isolated from Neem Tree and Their Applications. In: *Natural Bio-active Compounds: Volume 1: Production and Applications.* 2019. p. xxx. doi:10.1007/978-981-13-7154-7_17
26. Kumar A, Jose S, Hemalatha G, Tyagi D. *INTRODUCTION TO MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY.* A G PUBLISHING HOUSE; 2024.

HOW TO CITE: Anil Kumar*, Dharmendra Kumar Yadav, Ashwaraya Prakash, Rishav Raj, Richa Bharti, Lazor Murmu, FTIR-Based Comparative Study of *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh) leaves from Rajmahal Hills, Jharkhand for Phytochemical Constituents Evaluation, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (6), 934-941. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20959611>

